

Difference between homonyms and poly semantic words

Sattibayeva Surayyo Jaxongir qizi,
the teacher of Urgench
Ranch Technology Universitety
e-mail address: surayyosattiboyeva@gmail.com

Annotation. In this context, the rules on the differentiation of homonyms and multi-meaning words are touched upon, and many meanings are covered by the meaning transfer of words, what kind of connection they are with the meaning transfer.

Key words: monosemy, polysemy, own meaning , portable meaning, metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, function, lexical homonym

2) Words can have one meaning and multiple meanings. The phenomenon of ambiguity called monosemy. Single meaning words are called mono semantic words. man, words such as sparrow, ravish, camel have one meaning. Words with more than one meaning are called polysemous words. A lot words with multiple meanings are called poly semantic words. In polysemous words, start and will have a figurative meaning. The meaning of the words independent of the speech process is their own meaning date. The meaning of a word is to combine it with other words in speech gives portable meaning. For example: a person's ear has its own meaning, pot's ear- figurative meaning. Words with their own meaning and figurative meaning combine to form a figurative meaning does. Homonyms are pronounced and written the same, but have different meanings words that express are called formative words. Homonyms are the second name are fellows. For example: soz - musical instrument, soz - thoroughly agreeable, soz - inaq, close to each other. At first glance, cognate words look like words with multiple meanings. They should be distinguished from each other. Polysyllabic words are mobile. It is formed by using it in its own meaning. Similar words are two words with similar forms and more words. There are following types of homonyms. 1) Lexical homonyms are homonyms between words. Example: uzbek word 'Soch'- Hair-parts of body; 'soch'- spread(act.) 2) Phraseological (phrase) homonyms, i.e. have a figurative meaning and influence homonyms between

“CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES IN SCIENTIFIC INNOVATIVE RESEARCH”

Issue 5. May 2024

compounds. Example: To raise to the head = to quarrel. 3) Grammatical homonyms are of two types: a) Morphological homonyms are homonyms between adjectives. For example: ‘bags’ ‘-s’ plural noun’, ‘speaks’- here -s is verb affix for present simple 3rd person pronouns b) Syntactic homonyms are homonyms in phrases and sentences. Homonymy in word combinations:

yolg’ondan hayron bo’lmoq (astonished at lie),
yolg’ondan hayron bo’lmoq (to pretend to be surprised at smth).

There is a crucial difference between polysemic words and homonymic expressions. If you read or hear two words that are written or pronounced the same but have different meanings, they are likely to be either an example of polysemy or [homonymy](#). Deciding what kind of relationship the two words have can be challenging, but not once you understand the differences between these terms.

Polysemous words

- Refers to a word with multiple meanings.
- Are listed under a single dictionary entry.
- Must stem from the same [word class](#), eg noun-noun: mouse (an animal - computer device), wings (parts of birds for flying - part of a building), beam (a line of light - a piece of wood).

Homonymic words:

- Refers to words with different meanings but with the same pronunciation and/or [spelling](#).
- Are listed under multiple dictionary entries.
- Can be verb-noun combination: to address - an address, to rock - a rock, to park - a park.
- Study tip: Homonym is a broad term and can be distinguished from:

Homographs: words with different meanings and pronunciation but written the same, eg, lead (verb) and lead (noun)

**“CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES IN SCIENTIFIC
INNOVATIVE RESEARCH”**

Issue 5. May 2024

Homophones: words with different meanings and spellings but the same pronunciation, eg, write, right, and rite.

The main rule in distinguishing homonymous and polysemous words is determined according to the relatedness between them.

References:

1. U. Tursunov, A.Muxtorov, Sh. Raxmatullayev – Hozirgi o'zbek tili. Toshkent «O'zbekiston» nashriyoti – 1992 146-141b.
2. Shukurov Otabek Ona tili – Toshkent O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasi „Fan” nashriyoti davlat korxonasi – 2019 . 512 b.

**Research Science and
Innovation House**